

OUTDOOR GAMES AS A MEANS OF TEACHING ELEMENTS OF HANDBALL GAME FOR JUNIOR SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Annotation: The effectiveness of learning at any age largely depends on the interest of students and the provision of age-appropriate teaching methods and means. Since at primary school age a natural need is high motor activity and cognitive activity, it is necessary to look for adequate ways to realize this need. The leading type of learning for a primary school student is play; therefore, it should be used for effective learning.

Key words: outdoor games, handball, primary schoolchildren.

Introduction. The game of handball is built on natural movements (running, jumping, walking) and individual actions without the ball (turns, step-by-step, stopping, feinting movements), as well as using the ball (throwing the ball at goal, passing, catching) [2, 3, 4] . Rivalry, during which players need to attack the opponent's goal and defend their own, activates the use of all physical qualities important for a student: speed, flexibility, agility, strength and endurance [6]. Most of the functional systems of the child's body are included in the work, the main energy supply mechanisms begin to work [1, 5, 7]. To achieve high sports results, players must be decisive, result-oriented, persistent, courageous, and confident [8, 9].

Handball is a sports game, so after involving children in outdoor games with handball elements, it will be easier to learn the technique and tactics of the game than after generally accepted training sessions. When choosing outdoor games during handball training, younger schoolchildren should remember that the rules

should be as consistent as possible with this game and contribute to the development of the necessary qualities and abilities [10, 11].

Schoolchildren spend a lot of time at the computer, books, and doing homework. Nevertheless, in their free time from lessons, younger schoolchildren still devote enough time to playing. They use all types of natural movements, although they still do not know how to control their body, so they enjoy active outdoor games involving running, jumping, throwing and dribbling. All natural movements are better improved during play.

The priority place for classes on outdoor games for junior schoolchildren is a small space in which they can move chaotically, move in a circle, in a straight direction or in a “snake”, with a change in direction, running games like “run away - catch up”, games with jumping on one two legs, games with overcoming conventional obstacles (draw an “island”) and through objects (low bench, hoop); games with passing, fishing and throwing the ball at the range and at the target (volleyball, tennis), games with various imitative movements. All games are usually used separately, less often recess, and very rarely - in combination [12, 13, 14].

When analyzing the literature and summarizing practical experience, we found that in handball lessons, two models of outdoor games differ most: in the form of relay races and in the form of competitions among teams. A distinctive feature of relay races is that schoolchildren will advance for the entire team independently (one at a time) and in team competitions - in groups with the support and mutual assistance of partners, but without direct contact with opponents. The main components of relay races and games can be individual technical exercises of handball players or their different combinations, which students perform under certain conditions with different levels of difficulty. The main goal of the relay race is to perform as quickly as possible or better and more efficiently.

Learning to play must be divided into several stages using various exercises. At the beginning of training, the priority task is to develop the necessary skills for

dribbling the ball, feeling its properties and, depending on them, performing your movements.

Then you need to teach children how to hold the ball correctly with both and one hand, and place their fingers on the ball correctly. It is also necessary to teach schoolchildren to assume the basic position of a handball player [14].

When students have learned to correctly take a handball player's stance, hold the ball, and move around the court, they can begin learning how to handle the ball with both hands. One of the main actions with the ball is dribbling. By dribbling, handball players can move around the court in different directions. This helps the student keep his back. After this, you can begin to teach the student to "sit on his feet," that is, teach him to move in a defensive stance with his legs bent.

Passing and throwing the ball at goal are considered fairly similar movements. Therefore, starting to study throwing the ball at goal should be implemented in the same sequence as throws. During throwing training, attention should be paid to the fact that schoolchildren throw the ball, aiming in the correct stance of a handball player.

While playing, children learn the necessary motor skills and abilities, they develop courage, will, and ingenuity. For children of primary school age, the main focus is on the play method, which we can call a universal method of physical education.

The main provisions of the developed methodology for the initial study of handball elements for children of primary school age must be followed in the following sequence:

- mandatory division of a technical element into components;
- mandatory training in underwater exercises and simulation exercises before starting to study a specific technique;
- studying techniques, mainly using a holistic teaching method with the obligatory numerous repetitions of technical techniques in game situations;
- use of additional equipment and special markings;

- use lighter and smaller balls during the game.

During the experiment, various types of activities were organized with schoolchildren in physical education lessons: relay races with the ball, games in teams with the ball, dribbling the ball, shooting at the goal, games: “catch the ball”, “Pass the ball under the player”, “Fight for the ball”, “Loading watermelons”, “Ball in the goal”, “Catching in pairs”, “Knocking out”. As we can see from the list of games and exercises, at a certain period of time our joint activities were aimed at teaching younger schoolchildren the elements of the game of handball.

The essence of the methodology is six lessons in a cycle; each lesson ends with an outdoor game to reinforce a certain element studied during the lesson (throwing the ball, dribbling the ball). The last lesson is absolutely playful, where in different relay games we repeat and learn everything that we have learned in outdoor games and relay races.

Interest in outdoor games among children of primary school age has always been among the current problems of physical culture and sports [3, 8]. After all, the first involvement in physical activity and love for active leisure is formed in childhood [1]. And the most successful form, according to many authors, is gaming. When organizing a lesson using outdoor games among primary school students, it is necessary to take into account the risks that may arise in younger schoolchildren due to environmental influences and rapid fatigue, their anatomical and physiological characteristics. The child's skeleton has not yet formed. A significant layer of cartilage tissue determines the greater flexibility of bones, especially the spine. The muscles of the back and abdomen are relatively poorly developed, and the stability of the musculoskeletal system is also insignificant. When choosing outdoor games, preference should be given to games with different movements, without prolonged muscle tension [4].

The cardiovascular system of primary school children is distinguished by its greater capacity: the vessels are quite wide, while the walls of the vessels are elastic - this contributes to the good functioning of the heart muscle. But the functions of

the nervous system that regulate the functioning of the heart remain underdeveloped (mild excitation of the heart) [11].

As a result of a study of teaching the technique of handball movements, the author [1, 3, 4] notes injuries in the training process among school handball players.

Therefore, our research indicates that it is through outdoor games and relay races that children, while playing, improve the technique of performing movements in handball.

Conclusions. Researching the methodology for teaching elements of the handball game for primary schoolchildren based on the use of outdoor games, we came to the conclusion:

1. When studying the technical elements of the handball game, outdoor games with handball elements should be used to effectively master the motor skills of younger schoolchildren.
2. The results of the study indicate the appropriateness of teaching handball in several stages, using a variety of exercises.
3. It is methodologically justified to imitate a certain sequence during the initial study of handball elements for children of primary school age using outdoor games.

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